

successive treatment with quick-lime, potassium hydroxide pellets, magnesium and iodine and refluxing and distilling at each stage, as described in detail by Fieser¹⁰. The results clearly show that the concentration of bromine decreases with time, indicating reaction between bromine and methyl alcohol.

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4-Thiazolidinones. Part X

Syntheses of 3-(β -Aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-Alkoxyphenyl)-Imino-4-Thiazolidinones and 3-Benzyl-2-(2-Pyridyl/2-Thiazolyl/2-3-pyridylmethyl)-Imino-4-Thiazolidinones.

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IN continuation of our work on 4-thiazolidinones 3-(β -aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-alkoxyphenyl) imino-4-thiazolidinones and 2-benzyl-2-(2-pyridyl/2-thiazolyl/2-3-pyridyl methyl) imino-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared by condensation of monochloroacetic acid with:

- (i) 1-(β -aryloxyethyl)-3-(4-alkoxyphenyl)-2-thioureas;
- (ii) 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thioureas;
- (iii) 1-benzyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)-2-thioureas;
- (iv) 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridylmethyl)-2-thioureas; and
- (v) 1-benzyl-3-(3-pyridylmethyl)-2-thioureas.

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TABLE I. 3-(β -ARYLOXYETHYL)-3-(4-ALKOXYPHENYL)-2-THIOUREAS

No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	C ₂ H ₅	113	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.2	10.1
2.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	134	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.2
3.	4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	168	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.2
4.	2-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	131	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.6	9.7
5.	4-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	145-46	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.7	9.7
6.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	113	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.3	9.3
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	121	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.4	9.3
8.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	131	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.3	8.3
9.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	121	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.9	8.7
10.	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	112	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.1	9.3
11.	2-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	86-87	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.4	8.5
12.	4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	136	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.7	8.5
13.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	83	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.6	8.9
14.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	118	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.0	8.9
15.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	99	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.5	8.6
16.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	135	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.4	8.6
17.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	111	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.7	7.8
18.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	175	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.1	8.2
19.	H	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	98	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.8	8.9
20.	2-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	93	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.1	8.2
21.	4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	137	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.0	8.2
22.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	87-88	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.7	8.6
23.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	114-15	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.8	8.6
24.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	70	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.0	8.3
25.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	105-06	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.2	8.3
26.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	106	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.4	7.5
27.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	166	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.8	7.9

NOTES

TABLE 2. 1-BENZYL-3-(2-THIAZOLYL/2-PYRIDYL)-2-THIOUREAS

No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found.	Calcd.
1.	3-Cl	2-thiazolyl	136	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	22.3	22.5
2.	2-CH ₃	"	164	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₃ S ₂	24.1	24.3
3.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	176	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂	22.9	23.1
4.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	165	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂	22.8	23.1
5.	4-OCH ₃	"	140	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₃ OS ₂	22.6	22.9
6.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	2-pyridyl	135	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	11.7	11.8
7.	4-OCH ₃	"	126	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	11.5	11.7

TABLE 3. 3-(ARYLOXYETHYL)-2-(4-ALKOXYPHENYL)-IMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd
1.	H	C ₂ H ₅	84	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.9	9.0
2.	2-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	94	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	8.0	8.2
3.	4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	129	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	8.3	8.2
4.	2-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	122	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.5	8.6
5.	4-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	156	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.7	8.6
6.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	112	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.4	8.3
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	85	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.1	8.3
8.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	C ₂ H ₅	94	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.2	7.5
9.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	106	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.8	7.9
10.	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	82	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.2	8.3
11.	2-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	83-95	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.6	7.7
12.	4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	101	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.4	7.7
13.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	81	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.1	8.0
14.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	87	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.0	8.0
15.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	90	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.7	7.8
16.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	79	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.9	7.8
17.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.2	7.1
18.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	82	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.1	7.4
19.	H	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	83	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	8.1	8.0
20.	2-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	96-97	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.5	7.4
21.	4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	64-65	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.6	7.4
22.	2-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	80	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.7	7.8
23.	4-CH ₃	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.9	7.8
24.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	56	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.5	7.5
25.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	81	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	7.7	7.5
26.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	92	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	6.7	6.9
27.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	7.3	7.2

As the thioureas used are unsymmetrical, isomeric thiazolidinones are likely, but only one product was isolated in all cases^{1, 2, 3}.

Structures of the 4-thiazolidinones from (i), (ii) and (iii) were settled by analogy with the work of Dains *et al.*¹, Davis *et al.*² and Kharidia *et al.*³ 4-Thiazolidinones from (i) gave on hydrolysis 4-alkoxy aniline in solution indicating thereby that they are 3-(β-aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-alkoxyphenyl)imino-4-thiazolidinones.

Structures of the 4-thiazolidinones from (iv) and (v) were settled as follows:

1-(4-chlorobenzyl)-3-(2-pyridylmethyl)-2-thioureas was condensed with monochloroacetic acid and the product obtained was converted into its 5-benzal derivative. This was hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid to 2,4-thiazolidinedione which was shown to be identical with (m.p. 150°, mixed m.p. 150°) the 2,4-thiazolidinedione obtained by hydrolysing the 5-benzal derivative of the condensation product of

TABLE 4. 3-BENZYL-2-(2-PYRIDYL/2-THIAZOLYL/2-3-PYRIDYL METHYL)-IMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	2-pyridyl	117	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	11.3	11.3
2.	2-Cl	"	169	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ OS	10.4	10.1
3.	3-Cl	"	127	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ OS	10.3	10.1
4.	4-Cl	"	141	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ OS	10.3	10.1
5.	2-CH ₃	"	172	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	10.8	10.8
6.	3-CH ₃	"	94	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	10.7	10.8
7.	4-CH ₃	"	113-14	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	10.9	10.8
8.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	98	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.3	10.3
9.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	102	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.5	10.3
10.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	"	175	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.4	10.3
11.	4-OCH ₃	"	124	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.4	10.2
12.	H	2-thiazolyl	141	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS ₂	22.0	22.2
13.	2-Cl	"	125	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ OS ₂	19.6	19.8
14.	3-Cl	"	188	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ OS ₂	19.9	19.8
15.	4-Cl	"	174-75	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ OS ₂	19.5	19.8
16.	2-CH ₃	"	152	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	21.3	21.1
17.	3-CH ₃	"	121-22	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	21.2	21.1
18.	4-CH ₃	"	140	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	21.4	21.1
19.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	118	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	20.1	20.2
20.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	141	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	20.4	20.2
21.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	"	173	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	20.3	20.2
22.	4-OCH ₃	"	126	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ S ₂	20.0	20.1
23.	H	(α-pyridyl methyl)	88	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	10.9	10.8
24.	2-Cl	"	102	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.8	9.7
25.	3-Cl	"	96	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.9	9.7
26.	4-Cl	"	111	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.7	9.7
27.	2-CH ₃	"	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.4	10.3
28.	3-CH ₃	"	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.2	10.3
29.	4-CH ₃	"	119	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.5	10.3
30.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	97	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.9	9.8
31.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	145	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.8	9.8
32.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	"	83-84	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.8	9.8
33.	4-OCH ₃	"	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	9.6	9.8
34.	H	(β-pyridyl methyl)	106	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	10.9	10.8
35.	2-Cl	"	102	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.9	9.7
36.	3-Cl	"	97	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.8	9.7
37.	4-Cl	"	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS	9.5	9.7
38.	2-CH ₃	"	87	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.2	10.3
39.	4-CH ₃	"	97	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	10.4	10.3
40.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	95	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.9	9.8
41.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	"	138	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.6	9.8
42.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	"	128	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	9.7	9.8
43.	4-OCH ₃	"	114	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	9.7	9.7

1-(4-chlorobenzyl)-3-(4-chlorobenzyl)-2-thiourea and monochloroacetic acid. This proves that thiazolidinones obtained in (iv) are 3-benzyl-2-(2-pyridylmethyl)-imino-4-thiazolidinones. By analogy compounds obtained in (v) are also considered to be 3-benzyl-2-(3-pyridylmethyl)-imino-4-thiazolidinones.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

The required 1-(β-aryloxyethyl)-3-(4-alkoxyphenyl)-2-thioureas were prepared by the action of β-aryloxy ethylamines on 4-alkoxyphenylisothiocyanates by the

procedure described earlier⁴. These were recrystallised from alcohol and are shown in Table 1.

The required 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridyl)⁵/2-thiazolyl⁵/2-/3-pyridylmethyl⁶-2-thioureas were prepared as described earlier. The hitherto unknown thioureas prepared in the course of this work are shown in Table 2.

3-(β -aryloxyethyl)-2-(4-alkoxyphenyl)-imino-4-thiazolidinones and 3-Benzyl-2-(pyridyl)/2-thiazolyl/2-/3-pyridylmethyl-imino-4-thiazolidinones: These were prepared from the corresponding unsym. thioureas with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate as described earlier³.

Compounds prepared are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

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Book Reviews

JOURNAL OF RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Volume 1, No. 1, April 1973

After the advent of lasers there has been a great up surge in precise Raman work. The publication of this new international journal in an index of the magnitude such development. This journal will publish original work in all aspects of Raman spectroscopy including higher order processes, and also Brillouin and Rayleigh scattering. Six issues, published each year, will comprise one volume (about 600 pages). The editorial board consists of distinguished workers drawn from many countries including India. Both full papers and 'rapid communications' will be published. The present issue consists of eight full papers but no rapid communication'. It is not necessary to enter into discussions about the quality of individual papers. Suffice is to say that by the proverb, 'morning shows the day', we have a new journal with all the promise of

soundness and respectability. All institutions practising spectroscopy will undoubtedly but this journal on their subscriptin list. Additional expenditure for this is 67.83. US dollars per volume.

A good reviewer judges only scientific values and remains indifferent to other things. He shelves his sentiments. The present reviewer is unable to do so. True, Raman effect belongs to the world. But the reviewer is unable to forget that Raman belonged to this country where a Raman effect is discovered very very infrequently. The new journal will remind us time and again and again that this did happen at least once.

A. Chakravorty

TRACE CHARACTERIZATION : CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL NATIONAL BUREAU OF STANDARDS MONOGRAPH 100

Edited by W. Wayne Meinke and Bourdon F. Scribner

1967. pp. 579 ; \$ 4.50.

This Monograph has been published representing the report of the 1st materials research symposium held at the NBS Institute of Materials Research, Gaithersburg, Maryland, 1966. Symposia for trace characterization were devoted to lectures by outstanding authorities in the field and to the discussion of ninety contributed papers. The topics specially discussed, were electrical and electrochemical measurements; nuclear methods; optical mass, absorption and X-ray spectroscopy; electron and

X-ray diffraction; microscopy; and methods for sampling and preconcentration.

The monograph is well edited. The methods for trace characterization along with their up-to-date literature references are incorporated. This book will be of immense help, not only to the analysts in their respective fields but also to research workers. The price of the book is very moderate.

N. N. Ghosh